

A Novel Homozygous *CDH3* Variant Associated with Ectodermal Dysplasia and Bilateral Central Macular Dystrophy Without Ectrodactyly

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ABSTRACT

Ectodermal dysplasia with macular dystrophy (EDMD) is a rare genetic disorder caused by pathogenic variants in the *CDH3* gene, characterized by variable involvement of ectoderm-derived tissues and retinal structures. We report the clinical and molecular features of a 12-year-old girl born to consanguineous parents, presenting with severe hypotrichosis, generalized xerosis, trachyonychia, early dental eruption, and progressive visual acuity decline since childhood due to bilateral central macular dystrophy. Notably, no limb anomalies were observed, distinguishing this presentation from classical EEM syndrome. Whole-exome sequencing identified a novel homozygous splice-site variant in *CDH3* (NM_001793.6:c.867+1G>A), which was confirmed by Sanger sequencing. This case highlights the phenotypic variability of *CDH3*-related disorders and expands the recognized clinical spectrum, showing that macular and ectodermal involvement can occur independently of limb anomalies. These findings emphasize the importance of molecular diagnosis, genotype–phenotype correlation, genetic counseling, and multidisciplinary follow-up, including dermatology, ophthalmology, pediatric dentistry, and child psychiatry.

KEYWORDS: *CDH3*; Ectodermal dysplasia; Bilateral central macular dystrophy; hypotrichosis

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I. INTRODUCTION

Syndromic ectodermal dysplasias associated with limb anomalies and ocular involvement constitute a rare, clinically heterogeneous group of developmental disorders. The combination of ectodermal dysplasia, ectrodactyly, and macular dystrophy affects ectoderm-derived structures and neuroectodermal retinal tissues, reflecting early disruption of epithelial–mesenchymal interactions during embryogenesis [1].

Ectrodactyly, or split hand/foot malformation (SHFM), arises from defective formation of central digital rays, involving key developmental pathways such as TP63, WNT, and FGF signaling [2]. Macular dystrophy reflects progressive impairment of the retinal pigment epithelium and photoreceptors, related to genes expressed in both surface ectoderm and neuroectoderm [3].

Entities such as EEC syndrome (Ectrodactyly–Ectodermal dysplasia–Clefting) illustrate phenotypic overlap between

limb and ectodermal anomalies, though macular involvement is not always observed. The association with macular dystrophy may represent either an expanded spectrum of a known syndrome or a distinct genetic entity.

We report the clinical, ophthalmologic, and molecular features of a patient with this triad, highlighting diagnostic and genetic counseling considerations.

II. CASE REPORT

The proband was a 12-year-old girl, born to consanguineous parents (first-degree cousins), referred for evaluation of a suspected ectodermal disorder. She is the eldest of two siblings, with her younger sister exhibiting a similar phenotype.

Clinical examination revealed ectodermal dysplasia affecting the hair axis, characterized by severe congenital hypotrichosis: sparse, fine, short, and fragile scalp hair, with

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thinning of the eyebrows and eyelashes contributing to photophobia. Generalized xerosis and trachyonychia of the fingernails were also observed, along with early dental eruption. Visual acuity had progressively declined since childhood due to bilateral central macular dystrophy.

Whole-exome sequencing identified a novel homozygous pathogenic variant in CDH3 (NM_001793.6:c.867+1G>A, NP_001784.2:p.), which was confirmed by Sanger

sequencing. Based on the concordance with the clinical phenotype, a diagnosis of ectodermal dysplasia with ectrodactyly and macular dystrophy (OMIM:225280) was established. Familial segregation analysis is currently ongoing.

The patient was enrolled in a multidisciplinary follow-up program, including dermatology, pediatric dentistry, ophthalmology, and child psychiatry.

Figure 1 : (a,b) Scalp hypotrichosis characterized by sparse, fine, and fragile hair, consistent with hair shaft involvement in CDH3-related ectodermal dysplasia,(c) Hands with normal morphology, without ectrodactyly, (d) Scalp hypotrichosis in the patient's 3-year-old sister, with sparse and fragile hair, (e)Fundus photograph of the right eye showing central macular dystrophy, (f) Fundus photograph of the left eye showing central macular dystrophy.

DISCUSSION

We report a rare case of ectodermal dysplasia with macular dystrophy associated with a novel homozygous variant in CDH3, confirmed by whole-exome and Sanger sequencing. The patient presented with severe hypotrichosis, generalized xerosis, nail abnormalities, early dental eruption, and bilateral central macular dystrophy, but no limb malformations were observed, distinguishing this case from the classical EEM syndrome phenotype [4–6].

In the literature, Kjaer et al. described consanguineous families with homozygous CDH3 mutations causing typical EEM syndrome, including marked hand and foot malformations, highlighting the role of P-cadherin in ectodermal and limb development [4]. Senecky et al. and Balarin Silva et al. reported cases with combined hair, dental, and retinal abnormalities, with variable progression

of macular involvement [5,6]. Other reports, such as those by Jordan et al., show that hair and retinal involvement can predominate while limb anomalies are minimal or absent, illustrating the phenotypic variability associated with CDH3 variants [7].

Our observation thus expands the clinical spectrum of CDH3-related disorders, confirming that macular and ectodermal manifestations can occur independently of limb anomalies. It also highlights the utility of whole-exome sequencing in identifying rare pathogenic variants and underscores the importance of multidisciplinary follow-up, including dermatology, pediatric dentistry, ophthalmology, and child psychiatry. Ongoing familial segregation analysis will help confirm the pathogenicity of this variant and inform genetic counseling for the family.

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